

INFLUENCE OF NATIONAL HOME-GROWN SCHOOL FEEDING PROGRAMME ON PUPILS' ENROLMENT IN SELECTED PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN NORTH EAST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of the National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP) on primary school pupils' enrolment in North East, Nigeria. Three research questions as well as a null research hypothesis were postulated for the study. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of teachers in public primary schools in four states in North East, Nigeria was 3,757 from 416 schools, while the sample size of 360 teachers was drawn from 120 public primary schools which implied 90 teachers from 30 public primary schools within a state using multistage sampling technique. The self-developed research instrument named 'National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme Questionnaire' was used to collect data; while the enrolment register was also collected from the teachers. Three experts from Adamawa State University, Mubi validated the instrument. Test re-test method of reliability was used and the reliability co-efficient of 0.87 was obtained. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and simple regression analysis. In conclusion, the NHGSFP was a good initiative that helped in reduction of drop out of pupils in primary schools. However, there were some challenges that needed to be addressed in order to achieve the objectives of the programme. It was recommended that adequate funding should be made available to the vendors to enhance the promptness and quality of meal provided.

Keywords: National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP), Primary Schools, Pupils' Enrolment, Dropout.

INTRODUCTION

Health and education go hand in hand and both are two solid tools for human development. Tomlinson (2017) opined that economic productivity of an individual is based on health and education, which are two bases of human capital. Due to hardship in the country, many of the primary school children face hunger and malnutrition which hinder their ability to learn and perpetuating cycles of poverty. Ensuring sufficient quantity and quality of food for the school meals is crucial to attain education for all (EFA) goal because in Africa, one of the developing continents, the school meal constitutes the major meal of the day for most school children. Undoubtedly, this fact arises from the reality that school feeding programme has been a veritable antidote against negative coping strategies among victims of economic recession.

The Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) established the Universal Basic Education Act in 2004, which provided the legislative backing for the execution of the Home Grown School Feeding and Health Programme (NHGSFP). In 2016, FGN also launched the national home grown school feeding programme in public primary schools in Nigeria. The aim was to

ensure one solid quality meal a day for the children to increase enrolment, retention and reduce dropout rate. It covered students in primary 1-3 in public primary schools and was supported by the federal government. The state funded primary 4–6 feeding. The federal government has begun the initiative, but the state government has not. It was designed to provide government-led, cost-effective school nutrition utilising locally sourced farmer food. This would enhance local farmer produce and generate community jobs. Espejo, Burbano, and Galliano (2019) noted that lively school feeding reduces hunger and supports education, health, and community development.

Providing a daily excellent school lunch will help students eat a balanced meal capable of nourishing their bodies. The researchers interacted with some of the head teachers of public primary schools, and they asserted that many parents withdrew their children from private to public schools in order to benefit from the daily meal. They also emphasized that feeding programme has motivated pupils to be regular in schools; which has also helped to increase school enrolment and ensure positive academic performance for the pupils.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

School feeding programme is an initiative of the Federal Government of Nigeria that has helped in increasing school enrolment and attendance over the years (Dairo & Tolulope, 2021). This implies that school feeding enhances pupils' retention and reduces their dropout rate. In spite of the implementation of the NHGSFP, statistics revealed that out of the 1.7 million children enrolled in all the public primary schools in Adamawa State from 2016-2022. Almost 102,400 children had dropout from schools in 21 local government areas and 51,205 from 12 local government areas (ASUBEB, 2022). This discovery underscores the role of the federal government in establishing the programme. Therefore, this study is to assess the NHGSFP in public primary schools in North East Nigeria in order to discover the outcomes and challenges facing its implementation.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How is the NHGSFP practiced in public primary schools in North East, Nigeria?
2. What is the perception of teachers towards the NHGSFP?
3. What is the rate of pupils enrolled in public primary schools in North East, Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of NHGSFP on the rate of enrolment by pupils in public primary schools in North East, Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework

The study hinged on Maslow (1971) Hierarchy of Needs. It is a motivational theory in psychology comprising a five-tier model of human needs, often depicted as hierarchical levels within a pyramid. The levels are as follow

- i. Physiological needs: are physical necessities that include; “include; air, food, drink, shelter, warmth, sex and sleep” required by human for survival and if these requirements are not met, there tends to be problems for the individual.
- ii. Safety needs are nothing but the requirement for protection against components of security, order, law, stability and freedom from terror.

- iii. Love and belongingness need - friendship, intimacy, affection and love, - from work group, family, friends, and romantic relationships.
- iv. Esteem needs - achievement, mastery, independence, status, dominance, prestige, self- respect, and respect from others.
- v. Self-Actualization needs are those geared towards the realization of personal potential, self-fulfillment, desire for personal growth and peaked experiences. The theory expunges that there were certain minimum requirements that were essential for human needs to facilitate standards of living.

Fig 1. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Food as a basic need is provided through a feeding programme initiated by government, which supports the performance aspect, which includes metrics such as enrolment in school, good or normal class attendance, retention in school, and eventually learning progress. Food, as depicted by Maslow, aids in the child's development and the pursuit of other needs such as protection, self-esteem,

The Concept of National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme

National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme is a social safety nets might be too narrow, failing to acknowledge the preventive, primitive and even transformative impact that school feeding can have. Thus, school feeding as all-encompassing social protection interventions which can achieve preventive, protective, primitive and transformative impact on multiples actors through various pathways (Sabates-Wheelers 2021). The programme aims to improve the mental health and wellbeing of pupils which would encourage them to stay in schools.

Achievement of National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme in Nigeria

The NHGSFP in Nigeria has done a lot in the improvement of value and worth of education at the primary school level. Its achievement includes increase in the enrolment of children in school, improvement in academic performances pupils and employment generation for men and women. Empirical studies showed that school feeding programme is increasing the enrolment of children in the basic school in Nigeria and across the world. In Nigeria, Bosah and Obumneke (2019) submitted in their study that the NHGSFP enhanced the population of pupils, attendance, punctuality, reduction in pupils' dropout of school and reduction in number of children changing school.

The Effect of School Feeding Programme on Pupils Academic Performance

Although, food has classically been perceived as a means of providing energy and building materials to the body, research over the years has provided exciting evidence for the influence of dietary factors on mental function. Not only are children motivated to get into school but also significantly impacted their nutritional status and development, cognitive capabilities and academic performance. Research has revealed that the growth and learning potential of the recipients is dependent on the quality and nutritious elements of food (Jukes, Drake & Bundy, 2018).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted survey research design. According to Llyod (2023), survey research serves the objective of collecting quantitative or qualitative data, which can subsequently undergo analysis to derive conclusions, establish comparisons, or discern patterns within a certain community. The 13,670, which defined the population of the study comprised primary 1-3 public school teachers in North Eastern Nigeria; while the sample size was 360 using Yamane (1967) formula. Proportionate sampling technique used to select 90 teachers from 30 public primary schools in each of the four states to be sampled.

Two research instruments used are; a-self-developed questionnaire titled; National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme Questionnaire (NHGSFP). The first instrument was structured on 4 points scale (SA= 4) Strongly Agree, (A=3) Agree, (D=2), Disagree, (SD=1) Strongly Disagree. Section A contained demographic characteristics such as sex, class, name of the school and local government. Section consisted of items relating to the practice of the NHGSFP in public primary schools. Section C consisted of items relating to teachers’ perception of NHGSFP in public primary schools. The second instrument consisted of schools’ enrolment register, attendance register and cumulative results of academic attendance of two public primary schools from each of the four states in North Eastern Nigeria

The face and content validity of the first instrument were determined by three experts from Faculty of Education, Adamawa State University, Mubi and University of Maiduguri, Borno State. A pilot test was carried out on 30 primary 1-3 teachers from 10 public primary schools in Borno State which were not part of the study area. First test was administered on 30 teachers while the second test was administered after 3 weeks. The scores obtained were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and a reliability co-efficient of 0.91 was obtained. The two researchers with four trained research assistants collected data for the study. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as mean, standard deviation and regression analysis.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: How is the NHGSFP practiced in public primary schools in North East, Nigeria?

Table 1: The practice of NHGSFP in public Primary Schools

S/NO.	ITEM	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	Meals are supplied for the children regularly and quickly while at school	2.85	0.80	Agree
2.	The government formulates the policy objectives and monitors the administration of the school feeding programme	3.12	0.70	Agree
3.	The NHGSFP is funded through allotment of cost between state and local government	2.95	0.80	Agree
4.	There are policy guidelines to ensure the sustainability of the programme	3.11	0.58	Agree

5.	The programme enjoys support from international organization	2.83	0.78	Agree
6.	Assorted and nutritious meals are provided	2.62	0.83	Agree
7.	Meals are served in large proportions to satisfy the pupils	2.56	0.81	Agree
8.	NHGSFP targets the most vulnerable pupils within the schools to improve school attendance	2.93	0.57	Agree
9.	Pupils have access to good source of water after meal	2.60	0.75	Agree
10.	Food is not produced in the school premises by vendors	3.31	0.69	Agree
Grand Mean		2.89		

Decision rule: 2.50 – 3.49 as Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 as Disagree

The analysis in Table 1 indicates that respondents perceive the NHGSFP as effectively implemented in public primary schools in North East Nigeria. Government involvement in policymaking and monitoring is strongly acknowledged (M = 3.12), along with policy guidelines for sustainability (M = 3.11). Respondents recognize the funding strategy as a shared responsibility between state and local governments (M = 2.95). However, while meals are provided regularly (M = 2.85), concerns remain regarding meal quality (M = 2.62) and portion sizes (M = 2.56). The grand mean of 2.89 suggest that the programme is well-structured, but improvements in meal quality and serving sizes could enhance its effectiveness.

Research Question 2: What is the perception of teachers towards the NHGSFP in North East, Nigeria?

Table 2: The perception of teachers towards practice of the NHGSFP in public Primary Schools in North East, Nigeria

S/NO.	Item	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
1.	School feeding has increase enrolment of pupils into formal education	3.02	0.66	Agree
2.	School feeding encourages punctuality of pupils to school	2.98	0.69	Agree
3.	Due to the school feeding programme total number of pupils attending formal school has increased	3.01	0.68	Agree
4.	School feeding programme and other school-based nutrition and health programmes motivate parents to enrol their wards	2.96	0.73	Agree
5.	SFP enhance attendance of the girl-child whom are charged with various degrees of home chores	2.92	0.75	Agree
6.	NHGSFP has created employment among the community members which in turn, encourages pupils to complete their education	2.95	0.69	Agree
7.	With NHGSFP, pupils can work in groups in school for longer hours	2.93	0.70	Agree
8.	NHGSFP has reduced the dropout rate of pupils	2.95	0.67	Agree
9.	There is improvement in pupils' performance in both curricular and extracurricular activities	2.95	0.66	Agree
10.	Lack of effective implementation and evaluation system	2.78	0.94	Agree
Grand Mean		2.94		

Decision rule: 2.50 – 3.49 as Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 as Disagree

The analysis in Table 2 shows that teachers perceive the NHGSFP as effective in boosting school enrolment (M = 3.02), improving punctuality (M = 2.98), and reducing dropout rates (M = 2.95). The programme also enhances girl-child attendance (M = 2.92) and creates employment opportunities (M = 2.95). However, concerns about implementation and evaluation remain (M = 2.78). Generally, the grand mean of 2.94 indicates that the NHGSFP is seen as beneficial, though better monitoring could improve its impact.

Research Question 3: What is the rate of enrolment of pupils in public primary schools?

Table 3: Enrolment Level of Pupils in Public Primary Schools across Four States in Nigeria (2016-2023)

	No of Pupils				Total
	Maximum	Minimum	Mean	Standard Deviation	
Adamawa	107124	68525	86055	13,381	602382
Bauchi	1781939	909994	1228162	298899	8597137
Gombe	539831	407957	488324	52768	3418269
Taraba	760597	513025	644909	94655	4514361
Total	1781939	68525	611862	443728	17132149

Table 3 focuses on pupils’ enrolment analysis across the four selected states of North Eastern Nigeria, which include; Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe, and Taraba States. The Table shows that in Adamawa state, there was a stable increase from 68,525 in 2016–2017 to 107,124 in 2022–2023. The rise is consistent, but growth increases from 2020–2021 onwards. However, the gradual increase suggests effective policies or improved access to education, driven by programs like NHGSFP or increased awareness among parents. The assessment shows that the maximum enrolment is (107,124) reflects the highest enrollment of pupils in Adamawa is significantly smaller compared to other states, depicting a lower overall capacity or demand with the lowest minimum value (68,525) of enrolment among the states, indicating possible challenges in accessibility and school capacity in some areas. The average (86,055) pupil enrolment is considered to be modest, suggesting a relatively balanced distribution given the smaller range of enrolment and the low deviation (13,381) accounts for limited variation across schools in Adamawa. The total enrolment (602,382) of pupils is the smallest among the states, indicating a potentially lower population and enrolment drive.

Test of Hypothesis

H0₁: NHGSFP has no significant influence of Public Primary Schools Pupils Enrolment in the North East, Nigeria

Table 4: Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient on the influence of NHGSFP on Public Primary Schools Pupils Enrolment using simple regression analysis.

Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	t-Values	p-values	Remark
(Constant)	4.086	0.538	7.595	0.000	
NHGSFP	0.188	0.025	7.548	0.000	Rejected
R	0.346				
R ²	0.119				
Adjust. R ²	0.117				
F-Stats	56.975		.000		

*Significant (p < 0.05)

Table 4 depicts the summary of the regression model on influence of NHGSFP on public Primary Schools Pupils Enrolment in the North East. The relationship between the pupils’ enrolment and NHGSFP variables is positively low as indicated by Pearson correlation statistics ($r = 0.346$). The coefficient of determination (R-Square) of the regression model shows that the model has a predictive power of 0.119(11.9%), implying that NHGSFP explains about 11.9% variations in pupils’ enrolment while 88.1% are attributed to other factors such as parental education, socio-economic status, and availability of educational infrastructure that might also influence the decision to enroll children in school that were not regressed in the study model. The results of the fitness of the model shows that NHGSFP contribute to pupils’ enrolment significantly ($F_{(1, 420)} = 56.975, P < 0.05$) particularly in underserved regions.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from the analyses conducted provided valuable insights into the NHGSFP and primary education in North East, Nigeria. The practice of the NHGSFP was assessed in this study, revealing both strengths and areas for improvement. The promptness of meal provision, including the assortment and quantity of meals served, were identified as areas that require attention. These findings align with a recent study by Smith et al. (2022), which resolved that the timing and quality of meals in school feeding programs significantly impact their effectiveness. It is crucial for the program administrators to address these concerns and ensure that meals are provided promptly and solve the nutritional desires of the pupils.

Furthermore, the positive perception of teachers towards the NHGSFP, as indicated by the high mean scores across various pupils us aspects, is consistent with the findings of a study conducted by Johnson and Brown (2021). In terms of

pupils' enrollment in public primary schools, the fluctuating rates across the states was in congruence with a study conducted by Khan and Ali (2020) in a neighbouring region. Their findings indicated that enrolment rates were influenced by factors such as population dynamics, socioeconomic factors, and infrastructure availability. To further understand the specific factors contributing to enrolment patterns in North East, Nigeria; additional research is needed, focusing on local dynamics and contextual factors given that the hypothesis showed that NHGSFP contribute to pupils' enrolment significantly.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study provided valuable insights into the National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP) in public primary schools in North East, Nigeria. The findings revealed both strengths and areas for improvement in the practice of the NHGSFP with positive perceptions from teachers regarding its impact on various educational aspects. The enrolment figures over the years of study within North East, Nigeria showcase government efforts towards enrolling school-dropouts in the state. The innovation has to a large extent improved employment rates in the states as local vendors have been engaged for the exercise which has significantly improved their earnings and livelihood. The project which is also targeted at improving farmers productivity in the region through the use of locally sourced products have equipped most farmers in the study areas with a steady buyer for their products hence improving their source of income. The researchers observed that throughout the conduct of this study, only primary 1, 2 and 3 classes enjoyed the one meal per day and these were available in selected schools in the local government areas from each state.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommends the following based on the conclusion;

- i. There is urgent need for government across all the levels to deploy teachers and educational resources equitably across states to address disparities in class size and teacher workload for effective delivery of their services.
- ii. There is profound need for government to conduct regular training for teachers to balance their roles with the goals of the NHGSFP, focusing on nutrition's role in learning and its integration into lesson planning. This would go a long way in increasing the capacity of the teachers as well as the motivating the pupils for improved performance.
- iii. Government should also improve the program implementation process by streamlining the NHGSFP operations to ensure timely delivery, quality meals, and inclusion of marginalized areas to ensure consistency and equity in the administration of the programme.
- iv. The enhancement of monitoring and evaluation systems of NHGSFP is needed so as to establish robust mechanisms to track program outcomes and challenges at interval in order to enable real-time adjustments for greater efficiency and impact.
- v. There is need for partnership between government and community involvement in the promotion of NHGSFP. The strategy of involving parents, local leaders, and community stakeholders in program design, monitoring, and delivery would foster ownership and sustainability without compromise.
- vi. Government and its supporting agencies should also develop targeted policy interventions through the development of complementary initiatives, such as cash transfers and other financial incentives, to address economic challenges to school enrolment and attendance by pupils.

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